

Supplementary Information

Integrating enriched case data from national laboratory testing with population-based case-control analyses: a novel statistical likelihood-ratio methodology for PS4 applied to 325,345 breast cancer cases and 671,006 controls

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Supplementary Methods

Dataset Curation

For all datasets, variants were annotated according to the build 37 versions of MANE select transcripts for each gene (*BRCA1*: NM_007294.3/ENST00000357654.3, *BRCA2*: NM_000059.3/ENST00000544455.1, *PALB2*: NM_024675.3/ENST00000261584.4, *ATM*: NM_000051.3/ENST00000278616.4, *CHEK2*: NM_007194.3/ENST00000328354.6).

UK Biobank (UKB)

Per-patient whole exome sequencing data was accessed on 20/08/2025¹. In total, 18,477 female individuals with reported personal history of breast cancer (*in situ* or invasive, any grade or histological subtype), either self-reported or from linkage to national cancer registrations (cases), and all 419,373 individuals with no reported history of breast cancer (controls) were included. Data was curated as defined previously², with an additional filter to restrict to “White” ancestry (top-level self-reported parent ancestry, individuals associated with multiple ethnicities or “Other” removed).

CARRIERS Consortium

Per-patient summary-level data from 32,247 female patients with breast cancer (*in situ* or invasive) and 32,544 female controls from across 12 studies, filtered for “Non-Hispanic White” individuals. Methods for collection as previously described.³

BRIDGES Consortium

Per-variant summary-level data from 42,062 female patients with breast cancer (*in situ* or invasive) and 44,035 female controls from across 30 BCAC (Breast Cancer Association Consortium) studies

which recruited patients unselected for family history, and further filtered for individuals of European ancestry (<https://www.ccge.medschl.cam.ac.uk/breast-cancer-association-consortium-bcac/data-data-access/summary-results/bridges-summary-results>). Methods for collection of data as previously described.⁴

UK National Germline Data (NDRS)

Genetic testing data

Diagnostic and predictive germline testing data for *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* were and continue to be submitted by 17 NHS genetic testing laboratories centrally to the National Disease Registration Service (NDRS). Laboratories involved in submission are represented within the Cancer Variant Interpretation Group UK (CanVIG-UK). Variant submission was largely of pathogenic and likely pathogenic variants, with some laboratories also submitting VUS. *PALB2*, *ATM*, and *CHEK2* variants were also submitted from some laboratories, however were excluded from this analysis due to incomplete laboratory submissions for these genes, and the UK clinical testing focus for protein truncating variants for *ATM* and *CHEK2*.

Germline data collection was censored at 24/07/2024, with germline data available for some laboratories from 2000-2024. Data fields included the gene, coding DNA change, predicted protein impact, variant classification (where provided), and total count in full-screen/diagnostic tests (where one observation = one detection in an independently ascertained family). Variant nomenclature was verified using VariantValidator⁵. Variants where the gene and variant nomenclature did not match following the VariantValidator check, and the true variant could not be confidently identified, were removed from analysis.

Eligibility for genetic testing

In 2018, the National Genomic Test Directory for Rare and Inherited Disease was released.⁶ The directory included a set of eligibility criteria for offering genetic testing, including for patients with breast cancer under eligibility criteria R208. These criteria have changed over time (Box S1):

Living affected individual (proband) with breast cancer where the individual +/- family history meets one of the criteria. The proband has:

- a. Breast cancer (age <40 years), OR
- b. Bilateral breast cancer (age < 60 years), OR
- c. Triple negative breast cancer (age < 60 years), OR
- d. Assigned male at birth and affected with breast cancer (any age), OR
- e. Breast cancer (age <45 years) and a first degree relative with breast cancer (age <45 years), OR
- f. Combined pathology-adjusted Manchester score ≥ 15 or single gene pathology adjusted score of ≥ 10 or BOADICEA/CanRisk score $\geq 10\%$ OR
- g. Ashkenazi Jewish ancestry and breast cancer at any age
- h. ≥ 1 grandparent from Westray (Orkney) or Whalsay (Shetland) and breast cancer at any age

Box S1: Current eligibility criteria for R208: Inherited breast cancer for living patients with breast cancer, as per the National Genomic Test Directory for Rare and Inherited Disease, v8.1, July 2025

Cancer Registry

Individuals with breast cancer in England were identified using the National Cancer Registration Dataset (NCRD) which is managed by the National Cancer Registration and Analysis Service (NCRAS) and collects data on all cancer diagnoses in England.⁷ Breast cancer was defined as malignant neoplasm of the breast (ICD-10 C50), excluding stage 0 cases (Paget's disease), and/or

intraductal carcinoma in situ of breast (ICD-10 D05.1) provided these were high-grade cases (GH, G3, or G4). Other data collected included self-identified ethnicity and gender.

Cancer registry data from NCRAS was linked to the germline genetic testing dataset using pseudonymised identifiers based on NHS number, Date of Birth, and Postcode to identify 44,917 white, female breast cancer patients tested for *BRCA1* or *BRCA2* variants. Patients with a *BRCA1* or *BRCA2* variant who did not link to the cancer registry, had an ethnicity which was not “White”, or had a gender other than Female, were excluded from analysis.

Ambry Genetics (Ambry)

Diagnostic testing results from Ambry were censored at 25/03/2025. Per-patient summary-level data was collated from 187,642 self-reported “White”/“Caucasian” female patients with breast cancer, tested by Ambry Genetics for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*, *ATM* or *CHEK2* variants between 2015-2024. Variant nomenclature was verified using VariantValidator⁵. Variants where the gene and variant nomenclature did not match following the VariantValidator check, and the true variant could not be confidently identified, were removed from analysis. Liftover from build 38 to build 37 was performed for all variants to align with chromosome build used for all other datasets.

Breast cancer was defined as malignant neoplasm of the breast (ICD-10 C50). Other data included self-reported ethnicity, age at testing, sex, year tested, test name and code, gene, RefSeq transcript, coding DNA change, predicted protein impact, zygosity, classification, and the following information provided as binary ‘yes/no’ responses based on ICD-10 code: personal history of breast cancer, personal history of ovarian cancer, family history of breast cancer, family history of ovarian cancer. Patients were excluded if they had a self-reported ethnicity other than “White”/“Caucasian”, and/or were tested for a single site or single gene, as these patients may have been identified through cascade testing.

gnomAD v4.1.0

Data used to identify variants eligible for BA1

gnomAD v4.1.0 joint frequency VCF files were downloaded from the gnomAD website on 19/03/2025⁸. Variants with a filter of “PASS”, “EXOMES_FILTERED”, and “GENOMES_FILTERED” were included. VCF files were filtered for each gene using the following genomic coordinate ranges, per regions provided by gnomAD: *BRCA1*, 17:43044295-43170245; *BRCA2*, 13:32315086-32400268; *PALB2*, 16:23603160-23641310; *ATM*, 11:108223044-108369102; *CHEK2*, 22:28687742-28742422. The following fields were extracted from the VCF: #CHROM, POS, ID, REF, ALT, FILTER, faf95_max_joint, faf95_max_genomes, faf95_max_exomes

GroupMAX 95% filtering allele frequency (FAF) across all non-bottlenecked genetic ancestry groups (not including Amish, Ashkenazi Jewish, European Finnish, and Remaining Individuals) were extracted for all variants. The GroupMax FAF was compared to the maximum tolerated allele frequency (MTAF) for each gene, as defined by the respective gene variant curation expert group (VCEP); if the GroupMax FAF was higher than the gene MTAF, the variant was considered to have met stand-alone evidence criteria for benignity (BA1) and was added to a “BA1 list”. Liftover from build 38 to build 37 was performed for all variants in the BA1 list using Ensembl Assembly Converter (https://mart.ensembl.org/Homo_sapiens/Tools/AssemblyConverter). All variant nomenclature was validated using VariantValidator⁵.

Data used as population controls for case-control analysis

gnomAD v4.1.0 exome data VCF files were downloaded from the gnomAD website on 19/03/2025 (<https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/data>). Exome data files were chosen for this purpose as these files provide separate non-UKB counts, which avoids potential double-counting of controls with the UKB

dataset. VCF files were filtered for relevant gene regions as above for the joint frequency data. Variants in these regions were further filtered to require QC filter = "PASS".

The following fields were extracted from the VCF: #CHROM, POS, ID, REF, ALT, FILTER, AC_non_ukb_nfe, AN_non_ukb_nfe, nhomalt_non_ukb_nfe, and faf95_non_ukb_nfe. Allele counts were converted to individuals by removing n=1 count for each homozygous carrier instance, and allele number halved. Liftover from build 38 to build 37 was performed for all variants in the BA1 list using Ensembl Assembly Converter (https://mart.ensembl.org/Homo_sapiens/Tools/AssemblyConverter). All variant nomenclature was validated using VariantValidator⁵.

Dataset combination

Protein-truncating variants (PTVs) were defined as variants with one of the following variant effect consequences, annotated using Ensembl VEP⁹ (v112): "stop_gained", "splice_acceptor_variant", "splice_donor_variant", "frameshift_variant", "start_loss". PTVs that were in the final exon of a gene and/or splice variants that were excluded from primary analysis of the BRIDGES dataset⁴ were removed. Missense variants were defined as variants with a VEP consequence of "missense". All variant nomenclature was verified using VariantValidator^{5,10}.

All datasets were merged on gene name and coding DNA nomenclature. On creation of the combined dataset, the dataset was additionally merged with the list of BA1-eligible variants. Any variant present in the BA1-eligible variant list was removed.

The likelihood ratio cannot be modelled by PS4-LR-Calc where carrier counts are too large. 54 variants (of which 6 were missense variants: *ATM* c.1229T>C, *ATM* c.5071A>C, *ATM* c.5558A>T, *ATM* c.6067G>A, *ATM* c.998C>T, and *CHEK2* c.470T>C), had a carrier count >530 in the Ambry dataset or >2000 in the UK Biobank dataset and were not eligible for BA1 (see above), and PS4-LR-Calc could not be run. Therefore, these datasets were not included in the dataset combination for these 54 variants (retaining all data from other datasets where available).

Per-variant case-control analysis

Single dataset

Likelihood Ratio (LR) was calculated using the PS4-LR-Calc as published¹¹ using a default target odds of association of 4 for high-penetrance genes (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*), and 2 for moderate penetrance genes (*ATM*, *CHEK2*), as per published recommendations for high increased risk and moderate increased risk for breast cancer relative to the general population risk^{12,13}.

Fisher's exact test of independence and quantification of effect size using an odds ratio (OR) were used to test and measure the difference in carrier frequency between variant heterozygotes with breast cancer versus breast cancer unaffected individuals. The OR and 95% confidence intervals (lower 95% confidence interval = LCI, upper 95% confidence interval = UCI) were calculated as described above. Where variant carriers were only identified in controls, OR and respective confidence intervals are not calculated and are set to 0. Where variant carriers were only identified in cases, the Haldane-Anscombe correction was applied (+0.5 to each value) to enable OR calculation.

Unselected dataset meta-analysis

A meta-analysis was conducted using methodology as previously described². Briefly, data from the three unselected datasets (BRIDGES, CARRIERS, UKB) was used to calculate per-variant betas of association with breast cancer, OR, and standard error estimates with upper and lower 95% confidence intervals for each estimate where case data was available for at least two datasets. Meta-analysis was conducted using a fixed effect inverse-variance approach, unadjusted for age or other metrics from the constituent studies. *p*-values were derived from a Fisher exact test where there were

only two contributing datasets and at least one of the carrier counts was <6; otherwise, *p*-values were derived from a chi-squared test.

Where variant carriers were observed in cases only, the Haldane correction was applied (+0.5 to each value) to enable calculation of an OR. Where variant carriers were observed in controls only, data was not used to calculate an OR and not included in the meta-analysis to avoid generation of effect size where the variant was not seen in cases.

Combined dataset

For each variant, data available in each dataset was assessed for inclusion against the delineated rules (Table S14). After removing data which did not meet these rules, the LR from each dataset was combined as follows:

$$TotLR = LR_1 \times LR_2 \times LR_3 \dots \times LR_n$$

using data from *n* datasets for which an LR could be calculated. Where the combined likelihood was too small for storage within R systems, LR was set to the smallest stored value possible (5.0×10^{-324}). The total amount of evidence points was re-calculated for TotLR by way of log transformation (base 2.08), as per the Tavtigian et al. scaled point systems¹⁴.

Comparison of data for each gene was undertaken using the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test, and the Dunn test to identify which genes had statistically different distributions. To account for multiple testing, the Bonferroni-adjusted *p*-value for significance was set at 0.005.

Reclassification of missense VUS

As per the guidelines recommended by the ClinGen ENIGMA *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* Variant Curation Expert Panel (VCEP)¹², variants with results from high-throughput functional assays attained either strong evidence for PS3 or BS3 as assigned by the VCEP Specifications Table 9 (Table S15)¹⁵⁻²⁵. Variants in potentially clinically important functional domains (*BRCA1*: p.2-101, p.1391-1424, and p.1650-1857; *BRCA2*: p.10-40, p.2481-3186) with data from BayesDel²⁶ and SpliceAI²⁷ exceeding VCEP-recommended thresholds attained supporting evidence for PP3 or BP4 variants, thresholds detailed as follows (PP3: *BRCA1*: BayesDel no-AF score ≥ 0.28 OR SpliceAI ≥ 0.2 at any position; *BRCA2*: BayesDel no-AF score ≥ 0.30 OR SpliceAI ≥ 0.2 at any position. BP4: *BRCA1*: BayesDel no-AF score ≤ 0.15 AND SpliceAI ≤ 0.1 ; *BRCA2*: BayesDel no-AF score ≤ 0.18 AND SpliceAI ≤ 0.1).

Reduced penetrance criteria

Four criteria were defined to identify potentially reduced penetrance variants when comparing standard (OR ≥ 4) to reduced penetrance (OR ≥ 2) target odds of association. For any criteria to apply, a minimum change of two evidence strength categories was required.

- Evidence strength changes direction (Benign to Pathogenic)
- Loses benign evidence (Benign Moderate, Strong, or Very strong to No Evidence)
- Gains pathogenic evidence (No evidence to Pathogenic Moderate, Strong, or Very Strong)
- Substantially strengthens weakly pathogenic evidence (Pathogenic Moderate to Very Strong, or Pathogenic Supporting to Strong or Very Strong)

All criteria were defined based on the impact on an overall classification for a reduced penetrance variant in providing or strengthening evidence available towards pathogenicity. Where benign evidence was applicable at a standard target OR ≥ 4 but was removed at the reduced target OR ≥ 2 (criteria 2), use of a reduced penetrance target odds removes a potentially contradictory piece of evidence and thus better enables classification as pathogenic for a reduced penetrance variant.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: Boxplot of PS4-LLR evidence assigned for 1,712 rare PTVs included in the combined dataset. Each dot represents a single variant. Red dashed line represents 0 evidence points attained. 11 variants with PS4-LLR higher than +160 were set at +160. Statistically significant differences between average LLR for each gene are displayed (Kruskal-Wallis rank sum: $p\text{-value}=2.92\times 10^{-16}$, Bonferroni-adjusted $p\text{-value}$ threshold for significance=0.005)

Figure S2: Case-control LLR for variants classified as pathogenic, likely pathogenic, likely benign, or benign in ClinVar with at least 2 star classifications for each gene. A: *BRCA1* (Total number of variants (n) = 143). B: *BRCA2* (n=125). C: *PALB2* (n=2). D: *ATM* (n=33). E: *CHEK2* (n=5).

Figure S3: Sankey diagrams demonstrating difference of evidence application for rare missense variants at a target odds of 2 and 4. A: *BRCA1*; B: *BRCA2*; C: *PALB2*; D: *ATM*; E: *CHEK2*. P_VSTR=Pathogenic Very Strong; P_STR=Pathogenic Strong; P_MOD=Pathogenic Moderate; P_SUP=Pathogenic Supporting; B_VSTR=Benign Very Strong; B_STR=Benign Strong; B_MOD=Benign Moderate; B_SUP=Benign Supporting.

Figure S4: Case:control ratio for NDRS and UKB case series with varying proportions of 419,373 controls. The point at which case:control ratio is equal for both datasets is at a ratio of 1 case:6.62 controls (297,141 controls assigned to NDRS cases, and 122,232 controls assigned to UKB cases).

Figure S5: ACMG points applicable for 1, 2, or 3 observations in cases or controls at a target odds of association=4 for case:control ratios ranging from 0-12. A-C: Total controls exceed cases in a 10:1 ratio, with 0 case carriers, and either A: 1 control carrier; B: 2 control carriers; C: 3 control carriers. D-F: Total cases exceed controls in a 10:1 ratio, with 0 control carriers, and either D: 1 case carrier; E: 2 case carriers; F: 3 case carriers.

The size imbalance at which 0 ACMG points are applicable for each scenario is plotted as a solid black line. A ratio larger than this will produce “false positive” (when total controls exceed cases) or “false negative” (when total cases exceed controls) results for the respective observations of the variant. The number of ACMG points applicable for a dataset with a size discrepancy of 10x is plotted in red to demonstrate this concept; the size discrepancy produces false positive results in A and B, but not C.

Figure S6: Observed OR plotted against likelihood space for all combinations of 0-100 cases and 0-100 controls. OR=Observed Odds Ratio; LR_percent=Percentage of the binomial distribution covered by likelihood space; CI=95% confidence interval. A target odds of association of $OR \geq 4$ and target odds of non-association of $OR \leq 1$ was used. A case cohort denominator of 42,062 and control cohort denominator of 44,035 was used for each calculation. A: Plot of all case and control combinations. B: Plot of all case and control combinations which have an upper CI below 4 and a lower CI above 1.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1: Allele frequency of PTVs in each constituent dataset (unselected and enriched). EF=Enrichment Factor; CI=Confidence Interval.

		Unselected breast cancer datasets				NDRS				Ambry			
		No. cases with PTVs	Total tested	Allele Frequency	Average Allele Frequency	No. cases with PTVs	Total tested	Allele Frequency	EF (95% CI)	No. cases with PTVs	Total tested	Allele Frequency	EF (95% CI)
BRCA1	UKB	94	18477	0.005	0.007	1606	44917	0.036	4.87 (4.46-5.33)	3642	187642	0.019	2.65 (2.44-2.87)
	BRIDGES	427	42489	0.010									
	CARRIERS	164	32411	0.005									
BRCA2	UKB	242	18477	0.013	0.012	2165	44917	0.048	3.94 (3.67-4.23)	5688	187642	0.030	2.48 (2.33-2.64)
	BRIDGES	609	42489	0.014									
	CARRIERS	290	32411	0.009									
PALB2	UKB	105	18477	0.006	0.005	NA	NA	NA	NA	1646	187642	0.009	1.94 (1.74-2.15)
	BRIDGES	236	42489	0.006									
	CARRIERS	82	32411	0.003									
ATM	UKB	119	18477	0.006	0.006	NA	NA	NA	NA	2186	187642	0.012	2.03 (1.85-2.23)
	BRIDGES	269	42489	0.006									
	CARRIERS	147	32411	0.005									
CHEK2	UKB	231	18477	0.013	0.013	NA	NA	NA	NA	4539	187642	0.024	1.82 (1.71-1.93)
	BRIDGES	710	42489	0.017									
	CARRIERS	302	32411	0.009									

Table S2: All 13,829 rare PTV and missense variants identified, and PS4-LLR evidence applied for each ($OR \geq 4$ for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2*, and $OR \geq 2$ for *ATM* and *CHEK2*). For each dataset, the following information is provided: Case and control carrier and total counts, Allele Frequency (AF) in cases and controls, Odds Ratio (OR) with 95% Confidence Intervals, Fisher's exact p-value, Likelihood Ratio (LR), PS4-LLR evidence, and ACMG Evidence Strength. Where $n=0$ for variant carriers, the Haldane correction was applied before calculation of the observed OR and p-value. PS4-LLR was calculated by log conversion to base 2.08 of the LR. Please note that due to policies regarding identifiable information, variant counts for the UK Biobank dataset have been redacted.

[See separate Supplementary Table S2]

Table S3: Summary of all 3,135 rare PTVs identified for each gene, including variants removed before PS4-LLR was calculated.

		Rare PTVs included in final dataset (N=1,712)			Rare PTVs not included in final dataset (N=1,423)				Total number of rare PTVs in entire dataset (N=3,135)
		Evidence towards pathogenicity (LLR \geq 1)	No evidence applied	Evidence towards benignity (LLR \leq -1)	Single observation (cases or controls)	Variant only had benign evidence from NDRS set	Discrepant data caused by case:control imbalance	1 \geq OR \geq target odds (suspected reduced penetrance)	
<i>BRCA1</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	26	5	0	53	0	0	0	84
	CARRIERS	16	4	7	65	0	0	0	92
	BRIDGES	57	3	5	101	0	0	0	166
	NDRS	145	3	0	215	7	0	0	370
	AMBRY	119	122	37	118	0	0	0	396
	Combined	246	98	29	328	0	0	0	701
<i>BRCA2</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	61	16	11	87	0	0	1	176
	CARRIERS	39	7	6	103	0	0	1	156
	BRIDGES	69	10	21	224	0	0	1	325
	NDRS	217	10	0	289	24	0	1	541
	AMBRY	196	229	78	202	0	0	1	706
	Combined	388	187	78	520	3	0	1	1177
<i>PALB2</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	20	6	2	31	0	0	0	59
	CARRIERS	8	3	7	34	0	0	0	52
	BRIDGES	19	5	8	66	0	0	0	98
	AMBRY	124	5	29	58	0	0	0	216
	Combined	134	8	32	113	0	0	0	287
<i>ATM</i> (OR \geq 2)	UKB	46	10	4	91	0	18	0	169
	CARRIERS	16	12	10	81	0	0	0	119
	BRIDGES	27	26	13	134	0	0	0	200
	AMBRY	245	18	92	244	0	0	0	599
	Combined	281	25	105	363	0	3	0	777
<i>CHEK2</i> (OR \geq 2)	UKB	11	2	1	17	0	5	1	37
	CARRIERS	6	3	2	23	0	0	1	35
	BRIDGES	10	2	3	35	0	0	1	51
	AMBRY	61	4	19	78	0	0	1	163
	Combined	71	12	18	91	0	0	1	193

Table S4: Summary of all 10,694 rare missense variants identified for each gene, including variants removed before PS4-LLR was calculated.

		Rare missense variants included in final dataset (N=4,563)			Rare missense variants not included in final dataset (N=6,131)				Total number of rare missense variants in entire dataset (N=10,694)
		Evidence towards pathogenicity (LLR \geq 1)	No evidence applied	Evidence towards benignity (LLR \leq -1)	Single observation (cases or controls)	Variant only had benign evidence from NDRS set	Discrepant data caused by case:control imbalance	1 \geq OR \geq target odds (suspected reduced penetrance)	
<i>BRCA1</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	47	77	112	235	0	0	4	475
	CARRIERS	21	17	102	186	0	0	4	330
	BRIDGES	36	27	153	383	0	0	4	603
	NDRS	47	19	0	372	332	0	4	774
	AMBRY	67	84	429	699	0	0	4	1283
	Combined	127	91	565	1106	28	0	4	1921
<i>BRCA2</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	102	151	212	489	0	0	9	963
	CARRIERS	44	30	188	428	0	0	9	699
	BRIDGES	74	47	277	886	0	0	9	1293
	NDRS	63	34	0	679	675	0	9	1460
	AMBRY	108	170	851	1377	0	0	9	2515
	Combined	207	154	1128	2261	38	0	9	3797
<i>PALB2</i> (OR \geq 4)	UKB	54	55	66	174	0	0	1	350
	CARRIERS	13	10	86	136	0	0	1	246
	BRIDGES	26	22	97	262	0	0	1	408
	AMBRY	83	19	324	470	0	0	1	897
	Combined	84	35	421	628	0	0	1	1169
<i>ATM</i> (OR \geq 2)	UKB	136	100	95	467	0	90	1	889
	CARRIERS	76	91	109	354	0	0	1	631
	BRIDGES	95	123	155	691	0	0	1	1065
	AMBRY	285	61	736	1169	0	0	1	2252
	Combined	364	132	879	1673	0	14	1	3063
<i>CHEK2</i> (OR \geq 2)	UKB	51	26	18	84	0	22	3	204
	CARRIERS	31	32	22	115	0	0	3	203
	BRIDGES	38	39	54	150	0	0	2	283
	AMBRY	111	40	160	270	0	0	2	583
	Combined	140	41	195	359	0	6	3	744

Table S5: Summary of PS4-LLR applied for 26,758 ClinVar missense variants for the five genes of interest. Variants with Likely Benign, Likely Pathogenic, or Pathogenic classifications attained these with at least one star. PS4-LLR calculated using target odds of association for each gene (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*=4; *ATM*, *CHEK2*=2).

Gene	ClinVar Classification	PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity				PS4-LLR not applied/ applicable	PS4-LLR towards benignity				TOTAL
		vstr	str	mod	sup		sup	mod	str	vstr	
BRCA1	Pathogenic	9	5	2	5	39		1	1	2	64
	Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic	4	1	1	3	39		1	2		51
	Likely Pathogenic				2	71					73
	Conflicting Classifications	8	13	20	24	2191	16	52	110	197	2631
	Uncertain Significance	2	5	2	5	1583	3	9	22	43	1674
	Likely Benign					168			5	4	177
	Benign/Likely Benign					10				5	15
	Benign		1	2	2	56	2	5	3	73	144
BRCA2	Pathogenic	8	3			11			2		24
	Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic	6	6	1	4	15		1	1		34
	Likely Pathogenic	1			1	24					26
	Conflicting Classifications	7	31	38	50	3926	36	109	239	435	4871
	Uncertain Significance	3	11	14	8	3385	14	34	64	87	3620
	Likely Benign		1			205	2	2	4	4	218
	Benign/Likely Benign				1	15		2		6	24
	Benign	1	1		1	66		2	3	61	135
PALB2	Pathogenic							1			1
	Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic										0
	Likely Pathogenic					2					2
	Conflicting Classifications	2	1	17	8	254	10	22	44	109	467
	Uncertain Significance	3	4	14	28	2169	7	63	57	102	2447
	Likely Benign			1		30					31
	Benign/Likely Benign					6					6
	Benign					5	1				6
ATM	Pathogenic	1				5		1		1	8
	Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic	5	2	3	1	14	1	1	3		30
	Likely Pathogenic	3	1	2	1	29	1	2			39
	Conflicting Classifications	7	17	32	30	386	21	48	70	119	730
	Uncertain Significance	7	39	83	121	6320	67	197	203	117	7154
	Likely Benign			1	1	53		1		1	57
	Benign/Likely Benign					14				2	16
	Benign					13				2	15
CHEK2	Pathogenic										0
	Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic	1								2	3
	Likely Pathogenic	1			1	3					5
	Conflicting Classifications	12	3	6	8	41	5	10	10	23	118
	Uncertain Significance	11	22	21	51	1458	8	52	52	28	1703
	Likely Benign					8					8
	Benign/Likely Benign					2					2
	Benign										0

Table S6: 1,929 *BRCA1/BRCA2* missense variants (with VUS or conflicting classifications in ClinVar) annotated with PS4-LLR, functional data, and in silico predictive tool scores. Each variant has been assigned an overall classification using a) just functional and predictive data, and b) using case-control, functional, and predictive data. At least two pieces of concordant evidence were required for a classification, otherwise the variant was assigned a default classification of VUS. A target odds of pathogenicity of $OR \geq 4$ was used to calculate PS4-LLR for *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*.

[See separate Supplementary Table S6]

Table S7: All 357 rare missense variants flagged as potentially of reduced penetrance in high penetrance genes *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2*.

[See separate Supplementary Table S7]

Table S8: All 37 rare missense variants flagged as potentially of high penetrance in moderate penetrance genes *ATM* and *CHEK2*. Variants were flagged if they attained a PS4-LLR strength of pathogenic, very strong (P_VSTR) at a target odds of 2, and retained a PS4-LLR strength of at least pathogenic, strong (P_STR or P_VSTR) at a target odds of 4.

Gene	HGVS	PS4-LLR (Odds≥2)	ACMG Evidence Strength (Odds≥2)	PS4-LLR (Odds≥4)	ACMG Evidence Strength (Odds≥4)
ATM	c.7271T>G	64.55193	P_VSTR	57.54517	P_VSTR
ATM	c.6919C>T	104.0322	P_VSTR	47.07589	P_VSTR
ATM	c.1237C>A	20.6868	P_VSTR	20.58183	P_VSTR
ATM	c.8565_8566delinsAA	20.6868	P_VSTR	20.58183	P_VSTR
ATM	c.2446_2447delinsCT	13.43589	P_VSTR	13.20138	P_VSTR
ATM	c.7181C>T	13.43589	P_VSTR	13.20138	P_VSTR
ATM	c.5062A>G	12.52109	P_VSTR	12.26271	P_VSTR
ATM	c.3848T>C	14.22824	P_VSTR	11.65825	P_VSTR
ATM	c.7875_7876delinsGC	16.49809	P_VSTR	11.5506	P_VSTR
ATM	c.7355T>C	9.368159	P_VSTR	8.648262	P_VSTR
ATM	c.8122G>A	10.38935	P_VSTR	8.480891	P_VSTR
ATM	c.7328G>A	12.49302	P_VSTR	8.413735	P_VSTR
ATM	c.3998A>G	8.298999	P_VSTR	8.241108	P_VSTR
ATM	c.6315G>C	12.26825	P_VSTR	8.061289	P_VSTR
ATM	c.2443A>G	9.125543	P_VSTR	7.462444	P_STR
ATM	c.2260C>A	14.11902	P_VSTR	7.287471	P_STR
ATM	c.8737G>T	9.083161	P_VSTR	6.848976	P_STR
ATM	c.8194T>G	8.369433	P_VSTR	6.307137	P_STR
ATM	c.7291A>G	9.493449	P_VSTR	5.995528	P_STR
ATM	c.9022C>T	9.131487	P_VSTR	4.337908	P_STR
ATM	c.2849T>G	8.206288	P_VSTR	4.19504	P_STR
CHEK2	c.1030A>C	22.49407	P_VSTR	22.42994	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.904G>A	22.47074	P_VSTR	20.57442	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.1036C>T	26.50578	P_VSTR	17.57844	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.322T>C	11.76992	P_VSTR	9.659313	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.350G>A	11.53232	P_VSTR	9.575367	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.751A>T	21.28523	P_VSTR	9.391387	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.1034A>C	8.851866	P_VSTR	8.51299	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.253C>T	8.298755	P_VSTR	8.240856	P_VSTR
CHEK2	c.1180G>A	10.82446	P_VSTR	7.896421	P_STR
CHEK2	c.1448A>G	10.33711	P_VSTR	7.826636	P_STR
CHEK2	c.1037G>A	12.42795	P_VSTR	7.736061	P_STR
CHEK2	c.1205_1206delinsTC	8.470798	P_VSTR	7.525572	P_STR
CHEK2	c.707T>C	9.307548	P_VSTR	7.059749	P_STR
CHEK2	c.1270T>C	21.20859	P_VSTR	6.993337	P_STR
CHEK2	c.608A>G	8.073143	P_VSTR	5.960824	P_STR
CHEK2	c.952C>T	8.925006	P_VSTR	4.365145	P_STR

Table S9: Meta-analysed OR for 926 rare missense variants present in at least two of the three unselected datasets (UK Biobank, BRIDGES, CARRIERS). Where variant carriers were identified in cases and not controls (cases \geq 1, controls=0), the Haldane-Anscombe correction was applied (+0.5 to all cells). Where variant carriers were identified in controls and not cases (cases=0, controls \geq 1), data was not included in final meta-analysis.

[See separate Supplementary Table S9]

Table S10: Exemplar threshold differences between total cases and total controls (before false positive/negative results) at a range of target odds of pathogenicity, calibrated at 1, 2, or 3 observations in either cases or controls.

Target odds of association	Scenario		Threshold difference between total cases and controls
	No. case carriers	No. control carriers	
OR>2	0	1	3.45x number of controls
OR>2	0	2	5.50x number of controls
OR>2	0	3	7.55x number of controls
OR>2	1	0	1.7x number of cases
OR>2	2	0	2.75x number of cases
OR>2	3	0	3.8x number of cases
OR>3	0	1	4.25x number of controls
OR>3	0	2	6.85x number of controls
OR>3	0	3	9.45x number of controls
OR>3	1	0	1.4x number of cases
OR>3	2	0	2.30x number of cases
OR>3	3	0	3.15x number of cases
OR>4	0	1	4.95x number of controls
OR>4	0	2	8.00x number of controls
OR>4	0	3	11.1x number of controls
OR>4	1	0	1.25x number of cases
OR>4	2	0	2.00x number of cases
OR>4	3	0	2.75x number of cases
OR>6	0	1	6.2x number of controls
OR>6	0	2	10.10x number of controls
OR>6	0	3	14.05x number of controls
OR>6	1	0	1.05x number of cases
OR>6	2	0	1.70x number of cases
OR>6	3	0	2.35x number of cases
OR>8	0	1	7.3x number of controls
OR>8	0	2	11.95x number of controls
OR>8	0	3	16.65x number of controls
OR>8	1	0	0.9x number of cases
OR>8	2	0	1.50x number of cases
OR>8	3	0	2.1x number of cases
OR>10	0	1	8.25x number of controls
OR>10	0	2	13.60x number of controls
OR>10	0	3	19.05x number of controls
OR>10	1	0	0.85x number of cases
OR>10	2	0	1.35x number of cases
OR>10	3	0	1.9x number of cases
OR>16	0	1	10.8x number of controls
OR>16	0	2	18.05x number of controls
OR>16	0	3	25.55x number of controls
OR>16	1	0	0.7x number of cases
OR>16	2	0	1.15x number of cases
OR>16	3	0	1.6x number of cases
OR>100	0	1	32.05x number of controls
OR>100	0	2	58.05x number of controls
OR>100	0	3	85.55x number of controls
OR>100	1	0	0.3x number of cases
OR>100	2	0	0.60x number of cases
OR>100	3	0	0.85x number of cases
OR>1000	0	1	136.55x number of controls
OR>1000	0	2	281.55x number of controls
OR>1000	0	3	444.05x number of controls
OR>1000	1	0	0.15x number of cases
OR>1000	2	0	0.30x number of cases
OR>1000	3	0	0.45x number of cases

Table S11: Summary of 4,563 rare missense variants attaining PS4-LLR evidence at different target odds of pathogenicity, calculated for OR \geq 2 and OR \geq 4 for all genes

Gene		Target OR	
		2	4
BRCA1	P_VSTR	32	25
	P_STR	43	30
	P_MOD	71	28
	P_SUP	69	44
	NA	88	91
	B_SUP	45	20
	B_MOD	102	72
	B_STR	170	148
	B_VSTR	163	325
	BRCA2	P_VSTR	41
P_STR		74	56
P_MOD		140	57
P_SUP		109	67
NA		173	154
B_SUP		102	54
B_MOD		224	156
B_STR		322	322
B_VSTR		304	596
PALB2		P_VSTR	6
	P_STR	20	6
	P_MOD	51	35
	P_SUP	41	38
	NA	84	35
	B_SUP	29	18
	B_MOD	85	88
	B_STR	119	103
	B_VSTR	105	212
	ATM	P_VSTR	24
P_STR		61	34
P_MOD		125	74
P_SUP		154	47
NA		132	191
B_SUP		90	50
B_MOD		254	221
B_STR		289	234
B_VSTR		246	510
CHEK2		P_VSTR	25
	P_STR	26	18
	P_MOD	29	18
	P_SUP	60	44
	NA	41	46
	B_SUP	13	6
	B_MOD	63	50
	B_STR	66	53
	B_VSTR	53	133

Table S12: Alternative target odds for each gene, where all 13,829 variants are presented with PS4-LLR calculated for a range of target odds (target OR=2, OR=2, and a bespoke OR for each gene calculated in a previous large meta-analysis, where OR=8.73 for *BRCA1*, OR=5.68 for *BRCA2*, OR=4.30 for *PALB2*, OR=2.17 for *ATM*, and OR=2.44 for *CHEK2*).

[See separate Supplementary Table S12]

Table S13: List of *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2* PTVs with Pathogenic or Likely Pathogenic ClinVar classifications and strong or very strong Benign PS4-LLR evidence at $OR \geq 4$. The PS4-LLR evidence at $OR \geq 2$ is also provided to demonstrate weakening of benign evidence at lower target odds.

[See separate Supplementary Table S13]

Table S14: Summary of rules defined for inclusion of data from case-control datasets in case-control analysis using the PS4-LR-Calc.

Rule	Reason implemented	Application of rule
<p>Quantify enrichment of pathogenic variants in enriched case series</p>	<p>Clinically collected national laboratory data is likely to be enriched for pathogenic variant carriers due to restrictive eligibility criteria for testing compared to studies which did not select for ascertainment. This means findings are not directly comparable.</p>	<p>Enrichment of pathogenic variants can be estimated using the relative frequency of putatively pathogenic rare protein truncating variants (PTVs) in each dataset, defined as variants which met the criteria for PVS1 and did not meet the criteria for BA1 per the guidelines and frequency thresholds defined by the respective gene variant curation expert panel.</p> <p>For a given gene (g), the rare PTV allele frequency (AF) was calculated for each unselected case series. These frequencies were then averaged to give a per-gene AF for unselected breast cancer datasets ($gAF_{unselected}$). The allele frequency was similarly calculated for each laboratory case dataset ($gAF_{enriched}$).</p> <p>The gene-specific enrichment factor (gEF) was thus calculated for each enriched dataset (NDRS, Ambry) (Table S1), essentially calculating the risk ratio for rare PTVs in the enriched dataset:</p> $gEF = \frac{gAF_{enriched}}{gAF_{unselected}}$ <p>Lower (LCI) and upper (UCI) 95% confidence intervals were also calculated for each value of gEF:</p> $LCI = e^{\log(gEF) - (1.96 * \sqrt{(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{b} - \frac{1}{d}))}}; UCI = e^{\log(gEF) + (1.96 * \sqrt{(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{c} + \frac{1}{b} - \frac{1}{d}))}}$ <p>a = number of PTV carriers in gene g in enriched dataset c = total persons tested for gene g in enriched dataset b = number of PTV carriers in gene g in all three unselected datasets d = total persons tested for gene g in all three unselected datasets</p> <p>To incorporate this enrichment factor into the PS4-LR-Calc, the lower boundary for the hypothesis of association (p_l) was adjusted by the EF as follows:</p> $p_l = \frac{(gEFx)c}{(gEFx)c + d}$ <p>where the threshold (target) odds ratio (x) was multiplied by the EF. For <i>BRCA1</i>, <i>BRCA2</i>, and <i>PALB2</i>, $x=4$. For <i>ATM</i> and <i>CHEK2</i>, $x=2$. When likelihood was calculated for the unselected datasets, $gEF=1$, therefore having no impact.</p> <p>In this way, the minimum threshold for the hypothesis of association is raised for enriched datasets by the factor we estimate the dataset to be enriched, which ultimately means more case observations are needed to meet this threshold and assign pathogenic evidence. This accounted for the measured increase in pathogenic variant observations compared to unselected datasets, and allowed for direct combination of the final likelihood ratio for each dataset.</p>

Remove single observations only seen in one dataset	Single observations not repeated in multiple datasets are vulnerable to potential technical error from erroneous variant calling, and risk over-estimation of evidence strength resulting from the underlying binomial distribution when $n=1$.	LR produced from a single observation in a single dataset is disregarded. LR produced from single observations in multiple datasets are combined as normal. This approach is consistent with the direction of ClinGen groups such as the low-risk allele working group, and with other groups researching quantitation of case-control evidence such as the Zanti <i>et al.</i> approach, which require at least 3 observations of a variant before quantitative approaches are used for case-control data. ^{28,29}
Laboratory data must have equivalent, matched controls	A control set of observations is essential to perform a case:control calculation. Ethnicity-matching (and if possible location-matching) is also essential due to differing frequencies in variant frequency in different ancestral populations, particularly for founder variants.	For the NDRS case dataset, the control cohort from UKB (419,373 controls) was proportionally stochastically split between the 18,477 UKB cases and 44,917 NDRS cases. Maximising the number of controls in each partition while minimising the case:control ratio, 122,232 controls were retained for UKB cases and 297,141 used with NDRS cases (a ratio of 1:6.62 cases:controls for each) (Figure S4) All variant carriers in the UKB control series were randomly sampled between the NDRS and UKB datasets according to the same proportional split (29.2% probability to be in UKB control cohort, 70.8% probability to be in UK laboratory control cohort). NDRS cases were merged with the proportional split of UKB controls using gene and coding DNA nomenclature. We acknowledge that stochastic splitting of the UKB control series in this way potentially compounds any UKB-specific effects across two sets of case series (from NDRS and from UKB). However, at this time there are no other large, ethnicity- and location-matched control series available to use with the NDRS case series. For the Ambry case dataset, Ambry cases were merged with gnomAD v4.1.0 exome data using the gene and coding DNA nomenclature provided post-liftover to build 37. Notably, gnomAD data are population controls, not non-breast controls.
Evidence towards benignity may not be applied where the dataset is known to be depleted for benign variants	Benign and likely benign variants data is not routinely submitted from English laboratories to NDRS. Variant counts for these variants are therefore likely depleted, and evidence towards benignity would be inflated as a result.	After assigning equivalent matched controls from UK Biobank, evidence towards benignity ($PS4-LLR < 0$) in the NDRS dataset was excluded from dataset combination. Variants which were only present in the NDRS/UK Biobank dataset and which attained evidence towards benignity were excluded from analysis.
Constrain proportional size of cases and controls	Imbalance of cases and controls tested in the datasets led to application of pathogenic evidence when carriers were only identified in controls (i.e. false positive results), or benign evidence when carriers were only identified in cases (i.e. false negative results). This occurred when carrier count was low (<3).	False positive and false negative results only began to appear in the dataset when the size of the difference between total cases and total controls in the case:control dataset breached a certain threshold. This threshold difference is specific to a) the number of carriers, and b) the target odds of association. Therefore, we could calculate the threshold difference for a range of example target odds ratios when there were 1, 2, or 3 carriers (Table S10).

		<p>Threshold difference was calculated using a synthetic dataset comprising 5000 scenarios of different case:control sizes (where the smallest scenario was a dataset of 500 controls and 10,000 cases, and the largest was a dataset of 500,000 controls and 10,000 cases). For each scenario, the ratio between controls:cases was calculated (again, the smallest being 0.05:1 and the largest being 50:1). Each scenario was then assigned 1, 2, or 3 carriers in either cases or controls (with the other value set to 0, i.e. where 1 control carrier was assigned, 0 case carriers were assigned).</p> <p>For each scenario, PS4-LLR was then calculated. The scenario where PS4-LLR was closest to 0 was set as the maximum threshold difference before false positive/negative results are calculated (e.g. PS4-LLR being >0 for a scenario where variants were only seen in controls) (Figure S5). Interestingly, we found that at higher target odds of association, a larger number of controls compared to cases were necessary to avoid false negative outputs for variants only seen in cases (Table S10).</p> <p>For the actual datasets, all possible threshold differences were calculated for at every target odds of association when there were 1,2, or 3 carriers in either cases or controls. Where the number of carriers and the target odds of association caused the difference between number of cases and controls to exceed the threshold difference (thus producing a false positive/negative result), the data for that variant in that dataset was not used in the combined LR calculation.</p>
<p>Restrict inclusion by observed case-control signal</p>	<p>Variants with an observed odds ratio between the target odds of association and non-association (and with 95% confidence intervals also within these limits) have a <5% chance of the true underlying likelihood being more extreme than either target odds, and result in the total likelihood space (the percentage of the area under the binomial distribution being covered by each target odds) being very small. In these scenarios, slight differences in the number of case and control carriers can translate to inappropriately large likelihood estimates.</p> <p>It is highly likely these variants are of reduced penetrance compared to the standard target odds of association.</p>	<p>To explore this concept, the OR, LR, and likelihood space was calculated for every possible combination of 0-100 cases and 0-100 controls using a target odds of association of 4 and testing denominators based on the BRIDGES dataset (Figure S6a). Variants with an observed OR and 95% confidence intervals between the target odds of non-association (1) and target odds of association (4) form a group with the smallest likelihood space (Figure S6b).</p> <p>18 missense and 2 protein truncating variants in the combined dataset met this definition and were therefore excluded from downstream analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 <i>BRCA1</i> variants (c.4910C>T p.(Pro1637Leu), c.314A>G p.(Tyr105Cys), c.2315T>C p.(Val772Ala), c.2596C>T p.(Arg866Cys)) • 10 <i>BRCA2</i> variants (c.3545_3546del p.(Phe1182Ter), c.3326C>T p.(Ala1109Val), c.223G>C p.(Ala75Pro), c.3568C>T p.(Arg1190Trp), c.8917C>T p.(Arg2973Cys), c.6853A>G p.(Ile2285Val), c.6317T>C p.(Leu2106Pro), c.1964C>G p.(Pro655Arg), c.3151C>T p.(Ser1172Leu), c.1889C>T p.(Thr630Ile)) • 1 <i>PALB2</i> variant (c.656A>G p.(Asp219Gly)) • 1 <i>ATM</i> variant (c.4388T>G p.(Phe1463Cys)) • 4 <i>CHEK2</i> variants (c.444+1G>A, c.1312G>T p.(Asp438Tyr), c.1427C>T p.(Thr476Met), and previously reported low-risk allele <i>CHEK2</i> c.470T>C p.(Ile157Thr)¹³)

Table S15: All functional study data used in application of PS3 and BS3, evidence application for each variant as recommended by the ClinGen ENIGMA *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* Variant Curation Expert Panel (VCEP).

Study	Gene	PMID	Assay output (Functional)	Assay output (Loss of Function)
Bouwman et al., 2020	<i>BRCA1</i>	32546644	3x neutral, or 2x neutral and 1x intermediate	3x deleterious, or 2x deleterious + 1x intermediate result
Findlay et al., 2018	<i>BRCA1</i>	30209399	>-0.748	<-1.328
Fernandes et al., 2019	<i>BRCA1</i>	30765603	Mean ≥80% wild type activity	Mean <80% wild type activity
Petitalot et al., 2019	<i>BRCA1</i>	30257991	1P	3P
Starita et al., 2018	<i>BRCA1</i>	30219179	Zero depleted replicates	3-4 depleted replicates
Bouwman et al., 2013	<i>BRCA1</i>	23867111	Neutral	Deleterious
Mesman et al., 2019	<i>BRCA2</i>	29988080	Complementation shown	Complementation not shown
Richardson et al., 2021	<i>BRCA2</i>	33609447	>2.25	<1.78
Ikegami et al., 2020	<i>BRCA2</i>	32444794	Class 1 or 2	Class 4 or 5
Biswas et al., 2020	<i>BRCA2</i>	33293522	$P \leq 0.05$	$P > 0.99$
Hart et al., 2019	<i>BRCA2</i>	29884841	$FC \geq 2.41$	$FC \leq 1.66$

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